

Spectrum of Data Repositories

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We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

Information Entropy

Ecology and Management of Neotropical Migratory Birds

A Synthesis and Review of Critical Issues

Edited by Thomas E. Lovejoy and Deborah M. Stapanian

Tropical Bird Study From 1980

But...
Here are the data

The Long-tail of Environmental Data

Small

Different collection methods

Highly variable structure

Highly variable semantics

Long-Term collection

Bryan Heidorn, 2008. Shedding Light on the Dark Data in the Long Tail of Science. Library Trends 57

Why Does It Matter?

From:
Olivera R.M. et al.
(yesterday)
Systems
Architecture for
Analysis and
Visualization of
Atmospheric Data

Culture Change

Research Life Cycle

Context: <https://5stardata.info>

Research data in context

<https://5stardata.info>

Paper, tapes,
local hard
drive, email
exchange

Proprietary or ad
hoc databases.
Generalist repos:
Dryad, Figshare,
Zenodo, Github

Curated, in
a “domain”
repository
(e.g., EDI,
PANGEA)

Mission
data
(e.g.,
satellite)

Repository Role

Repository Operations

Services

Curation, archive

Metadata for aggregation

Publication linkages

Training

DataONE

SCHOLIX

Responsibility

Carroll S.
et al 2020

Lin et al, 2020.

TRUST

- Transparency - clarify terms of use, practices, timeframe
- Responsibility - adhere to stewardship standards
- User Focus - meet community expectations
- Sustainability - mitigate risk, continuity, succession
- Technology - provide secure, persistent, reliable services

Findability, reusability

Generalists

Domain
Specific
Citation
metadata

Domain
Specific
Science
metadata

Specialized
format and
metadata

Metadata and data formatting requirements

Metadata Aggregators

44 MEMBER
REPOSITORIES

Portal Brasileiro de Publicações
e Dados Científicos em Acesso Aberto

Data Sources 12 sources returned [Export to CSV](#)

[All sources](#) 1,430

[Digital Library of Monographs](#) 3

[Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations](#) 66

[Aggregator Portal](#) 1

[Book Portal](#) 9

[Research Data Repository](#) 12

Search Sort [Ascen](#)

- Comunidade Dados de Pesquisa do Repositório CEDAP da UFRGS
Responsible institution: Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS)
Number of collected documents: 0
- COVID-19 Data Sharing/BR
Responsible institution: Fundação de Amparo à Pesquisa do Estado de São Paulo (Fapesp)
Number of collected documents: 5

DataONE Data Services Community Learning About

Clear all filters

Search

Filter by:

- Data attribute
- Annotation
- Data files
- Member Node
- Creator
- Year
- Identifier
- Taxon

Location

Hide Map Limit m

82 452 243

985 217 74

1778 43 217

1230 48 72

409 37 428

Satellite Terrain 25

Google Keyboard shortcuts Map data

Tânia P. Pimentel and Carolina V. Castilho. **Profundidade do lençol freático (piezômetros) no Parque Nacional do Viruá (Caracarái, Roraima), 2019-2021.** Programa de Pesquisa em Biodiversidade (PPBio). PPBioAmOc.673.4.

Bruno Cascardo Pereira and Helena de Godoy Bergallo. **Mammalian encounter rates in transect surveys / Taxas de encontro de mamíferos em transecções.** Programa de Pesquisa em Biodiversidade (PPBio). PPBioMA.59.16.

Viviana Marcela Varón-Ramírez, Gustavo A. Araujo-Carrillo, and Mario Guevara. 2022. **Textural soil maps, Colombia, 0 - 100 cm.** Environmental Data Initiative. <https://pasta.lternet.edu/package/metadata/eml/edi/972/3>.

Viviana Marcela Varón-Ramírez and Gustavo A. Araujo-Carrillo. 2022. **Textural soil data, Colombia, 0 - 100 cm.** Environmental Data Initiative.

Data Assessment

Lukas M. Lamb and Tiffany G. Troxler. 2022. [Survey of biological, geomorphic, and hydrologic properties across ecosystem states in a non-tidal, salinizing peat marsh in Everglades National Park, Florida, USA: 2019–2020](#). LTER Network Member Node.

<https://pasta.lternet.edu/package/metadata/eml/knb-lter-fce/1250/1>.

After running your metadata against our standard set of metadata, data, and congruency checks, we have found the following potential issues. Please assist us in improving the discoverability and reusability of your research data by addressing the issues below.

Assessment suite: FAIR Suite v0.3.1

Checking adherence to FAIR principles

Liang, Elshanawany, Rehab, Fischer, Helmut W, Hoins, Mirja, et al. 2018. [of sediment core GeoB10732-3](#). PANGAEA Data Publisher for Earth and [0.1594/PANGAEA.779523](#).

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Assessment suite: FAIR Suite v0.3.1

How to Find a Repository

re3data.org
REGISTRY OF RESEARCH DATA REPOSITORIES

environmental data

🔍 Search

Get Involved

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

A Decade of Data 2013-2023

Research Data Alliance

'A Decade of Data':

*Celebrating 10 Years of the
Research Data Alliance*

Learn more about upcoming
international and regional events

Conclusions (Data Creators)

Something bad will happen

- Forgetfulness
- Drive failure
- Aging proprietary software

Deposit your data in a reliable repository as soon
as you can

In papers, cite the data you use

Conclusions (Data Users)

There is lots of research-grade data, but it's not always easy to find or use

Any future use depends on high quality metadata at the source

Features that push research data into the realm of “linked data” - making it available for multiple unknown uses - require technical solutions and informatics professionals

Research data could be more easily incorporated into systems like predictive models. We need well-described use cases to prioritize data sets and define details - and that are followed up with funding

References

Michener, William & Brunt, James & Helly, John & Kirchner, Thomas & Stafford, Susan. 1997. Non-geospatial metadata for the ecological sciences. *Ecological Applications*. 7. 330-342.

Heidorn, Bryan. 2008. Shedding Light on the Dark Data in the Long Tail of Science. *Library Trends* 57

Carroll S. et al 2020. Implementing the CARE Principles: The CARE-full Process. Joint Meeting - International Indigenous Data Sovereignty IG and FAIR Data Maturity Model WG: Implementing the CARE Principles: The CARE-full Process. RDA 16th Plenary, 2020-11-12.

Lin et al, 2020. The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

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